

Effectiveness of Interventions to Reduce Carbon-Emissions within Secondary Healthcare

The Climate emergency is also a health emergency,¹ with climate change impacting directly on human health through climate events such as earthquakes and heatwaves, and indirectly through health consequences such as increased prevalence of respiratory conditions due to air pollution.²

Healthcare services have a larger carbon footprint than aviation and shipping combined, responsible for estimated 4-5% of global carbon emissions.³ In 2008, the Climate Change Act set national targets for 100 percent reduction of carbon emissions in England of 1990 levels by 2050.⁵ The National Health Service (NHS) has an important role fulfilling these targets, as it accounts for 4% of England's carbon-footprint,⁴ with the majority of carbon-emissions arising from acute care.⁶ To support this work, evidence evaluating interventions to reduce carbon emissions within secondary healthcare is needed. This evidence should consider patient outcomes and cost-effectiveness along the patient pathway to identify strategies that take into account the wider healthcare systems.

This systematic review includes primary research evaluating the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of interventions to reduce the carbon footprint of medical interventions carried out in secondary healthcare.

The review, which included 89 studies, was requested by the **Greener NHS team at NHS England**. Findings highlight:

- ◆ **Most research has been conducted in:** Urology (n=14), Gastroenterology (n=13), Oncology (n=13) and Renal (n=11).
- ◆ **Most common studied intervention is Telehealth** (n=26). Telehealth technology could reduce carbon-emissions when compared with face-to-face care. However, carbon calculations often only considered patient-travel and didn't include emissions associated with delivering other parts of the service or impact on wider patient care pathway.
- ◆ **Heterogeneity between types of interventions within individual specialties and methods used to calculate carbon-emissions** limited conclusions as to which interventions may be most effective in reducing carbon emissions. **Patient clinical/ satisfaction** and **financial** outcomes alongside carbon emission data were limited.
- ◆ **Across most clinical specialties, the majority of evidence was found in the first three stages of the patient care journey;** 1) initial assessment/diagnostic tests, 2) initial treatment or 3) follow-up. For the renal specialty, most evidence was within ongoing care.
- ◆ **Carbon-emissions were reduced with reuseable equipment** vs disposable options, although there is some uncertainty regarding these findings within the urology specialty.
- ◆ We produced an [evidence and gap map](#), showing where evidence informs the patient care pathway.

Medical specialties of interest:

- Cardiology
- Gastroenterology
- Ophthalmology
- Orthopedics and trauma
- Renal
- Respiratory
- High volume, low complexity surgery:
 - ◇ Ear, nose and throat
 - ◇ Gynecology
 - ◇ Urology

QR code; map of
review evidence

How did we do this review?

Finding the literature:

We searched bibliographic databases covering health care and environmental science journals, and inspected the HealthcareLCA database. We conducted forwards and backwards citation chasing on all included studies and searched reference lists of topically relevant reviews, Google Scholar and relevant websites.

Eligibility criteria:

Primary research evaluating interventions to reduce carbon-emissions relating to any procedure, process, treatment or pathway in relevant specialties within secondary healthcare.

Study selection, data extraction and study quality appraisal:

Screening, data extraction and quality appraisal of LCA studies were completed by two reviewers.

Synthesis:

Interventions were classified into **5 broad categories**:

1. Accessing care
2. Care setting
3. Product level
4. Care delivery
5. Multiple components

Figure 1: Stages of a Life-Cycle Assessment

Within each of the five intervention categories, studies were grouped according to whether they used Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA) methods to calculate carbon-emissions or not. Stages of an LCA are shown in Figure 1.²²

We produced an **evidence and gap map** to present how included studies aligned with a simplified patient care pathway within each specialty.

Overview of the evidence

Intervention	Number of studies
Accessing care	29
Telehealth	
Treatment pathway	
De centralized care	
Product level	17
Reuseable equipment	
Equipment type	
Care delivery	16
Treatment regimen	
Surgical procedure	
Setting	20
Waste management	
Energy conservation	
Combination	7

Eighty-nine studies (93 articles) were included. Thirty-three (33) studies were conducted within the UK.

Twenty-nine (29) studies used Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) informed methods to calculate carbon emission, 19 of these utilized a full LCA approach comprising both:

1. An **inventory analysis**, evaluating the energy consumption, emissions and resource associated with an intervention throughout the life-cycle stage of the product, process or activity, and;
2. An **impact assessment**, converting inventory data from the life cycle assessment into a set of potential impacts on the environment (e.g. carbon emissions, eutrophication, ecosystem quality, non-renewable resources etc.).

Ten (10) studies were appraised as 'High' quality, 14 as 'Medium' quality and five as 'Low' quality. Of the 33 studies conducted within the UK, one of these used full LCA methodology.

Interventions evaluated in this review

What did we find?

Accessing care (29 studies)

Three (3) studies were informed by LCA methodology. Two were appraised as 'High' and one as 'Medium' quality. The most common specialties are urology (n=5), orthopaedics (n=4) and oncology/radiation oncology (n=6)

Telehealth was the most commonly evaluated intervention (n=26) and was associated with reduced carbon emissions when compared to face-to-face care. However, most of the studies used non-LCA methodology (n=24) and were based on carbon-emission calculations focusing primarily on patient travel savings without considering carbon emissions from other parts of the system. Patient travel distance and time saved were the most common patient reported outcomes. The majority of patient and financial outcomes favoured the telemedicine intervention, although most were based on descriptive or narrative analyses.

Thirteen LCA studies, appraised as predominantly 'High' or 'Medium' quality, used LCA or inventory analysis methods to explore carbon emissions associated with reuseable equipment.

Carbon-emissions were reduced with reuseable equipment vs disposable options, although there is some uncertainty with respect to these findings within the urology speciality. Patient reported outcomes were limited.

Two studies within gastroenterology settings concluded that reuseable/hybrid equipment cost less than disposable. Heterogeneity of interventions in 3 studies focusing on changing equipment type prevented meaningful synthesis.

Product-level (17 studies)

Care delivery (16 studies)

Five non-LCA studies evaluated the impact of altering the treatment regimen for patients undergoing cancer treatment. Five non-LCA studies and one 'Medium' quality LCA study evaluated carbon emissions associated with changes to the patient treatment pathway. Three LCA studies (two of 'Medium', one of 'High' quality) and one non-LCA studies evaluated changes in surgical procedures.

All studies indicated reduced carbon emissions were associated with treatment schedules which reduced the number of times patients were required to travel to hospital. Patient and cost outcomes were limited, with the majority calculated using narrative or descriptive statistics.

Four studies used LCA informed methodology, one appraised as 'High', two as 'Medium' and one as 'Low' quality.

Overall, whilst waste management/reduction interventions were associated with reduced carbon emissions (n=12), interventions were highly heterogeneous with limited consideration of patient or cost outcomes. Seven non-LCA studies found reduced carbon emissions were associated with energy conservation interventions, the majority of which were conducted within radiology/radiotherapy settings.

Care setting (20 studies)

Multiple- components

Heterogeneity across types of specialties and intervention precluded meaningful synthesis.

What are the implications of this review?

This systematic review aimed to examine the effectiveness of interventions in reducing the carbon footprint within medical specialties in secondary healthcare. This evidence is presented in an interactive [evidence-and-gap](#) map. Implications of the findings include:

◆ Policy makers, clinicians and commissioners:

- ◇ The evidence and gap map displays the evidence included in this review as it relates to the patient care pathway for each specialty, enabling evidence users to locate evidence relevant to their interests and requirements, which may help inform future clinical practice and commissioning of research.

◆ Future research should address:

- ◇ The importance of considering how to reduce carbon emissions associated with the processes (manufacture, transport and reprocessing or disposal) or equipment, including a particular focus on hotspots in manufacturing of disposable equipment and reprocessing of reusable products.
- ◇ Gaps highlighted in the evidence and gap map, particularly relating to (i) the ongoing care or discharge of patients or (ii) relating to obstetric, respiratory and ICU specialties where little evidence was found.
- ◇ The need to ensure individuals conducting LCA studies have the support and resources required to implement within healthcare settings, and report conduct/findings in a way which maintains transparency on methodological and system boundaries.
- ◇ The need to develop guidelines to demonstrate which factors need to be considered within each intervention / specialty (with a full patient care perspective).
- ◇ The importance of evaluating carbon-emissions alongside patient care/ experience and cost outcomes.
- ◇ The importance of evaluating the digital carbon footprint associated with telehealth care, whilst ensuring effective use of technology to maximize patient outcomes/cost-benefits across primary and secondary care.

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[Link to Full Report](#)

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